

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report describes the recommended workflow for the Next Generation ESMs (experiment setup -> simulation -> output ->analysis), based on the lessons learned from Hackathons in the Development and Application Phases.

Work package in charge:

WP3

Lead author:

Janos Zimmermann (DKRZ)

Other contributing authors:

Thomas Rackow (ECMWF)

Karl-Hermann Wieners (MPI-M)

Florian Ziemer (DKRZ)

Internal reviewer(s):

1st reviewer: Phillipp Weiss

2nd reviewer: Tobias Kölling

Contacts: zimmermann@dkrz.de

Visit us on: www.nextgems-h2020.eu

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Executive summary

This report outlines workflows of the Horizon 2020 project nextGEMS that have proven successful and that have the potential to be useful for the Digital Twins. Digital Twins, as exemplified by the Destination Earth (DestinE) initiative, are high-resolution, continuously updated digital replicas of the Earth system that support advanced climate prediction and scenario analysis. The main improvement regarding workflows was achieved in the main setup and data provision together with many small additions to make everything work fine in the end.

The report lays down which key parts improved the workflows most and how they were achieved. There are furthermore examples given, how data provision works and examples how easy it became to work with large amounts of climate data across two common Earth system models (ESM). The central ideas are outlined in section 1.1.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP3	Relevance in this deliverable?
To complete Cycle 3 (Development) simulations (O1).	yes
To finalize the configuration (including associated output and data management requirements) of SR-ESMs for the production simulations (O1).	no
To perform present day and future projections (i.e., production simulations). (O1/O2)	yes
To organize and curate simulation output for sustainable access beyond the completion of NextGEMS. (O1/O2/O3)	no
To support the four themes in exploring extensions of SR-ESMs to address additional application needs and testing proposed model improvements. (O1/O2/O3)	yes

1 Detailed report on the deliverable

1.1 Central ideas

This report outlines the core principles behind building workflows for the next-generation Earth System Models (ESMs), with a particular focus on preparing for future applications such as Digital Twins. Our approach is designed to support new and emerging workflows while preserving backward compatibility, allowing established practices and data pipelines to remain functional as technology evolves.

Previous approaches to data provision have often placed convenience for data producers above the needs of data consumers, resulting in fragmented or inefficient workflows. Here, we invest additional effort upfront to create well-structured, user-friendly datasets that serve the broader scientific community more effectively. Specifically, by adopting the zarr¹ format for cloud-native, chunked storage of large, coherent datasets and leveraging HEALPix (Górski et al., 2005) as a common, equal-area analysis grid, we facilitate seamless cross-model comparison, scalable analysis, and interoperability between research teams. This design also enables subsetting, aggregation, and multi-resolution access which is crucial for both exploratory research and operational workflows.

A central element in the nextGEMS workflows are the hackathons, where about 100 scientists meet and analyze newly generated datasets with on-site support of the modeling teams and technical staff of the German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ). This creates a very tight feedback loop between the users and the providers of the datasets and allows for fast development and major overhauls of the workflows, improving the users' experience with each iteration.

Furthermore, our strategy encompasses the entire dataset life cycle: from initial simulation output and postprocessing, through distribution via accessible catalogs and public access via object stores to long-term storage. By integrating catalogs, layered storage systems and lowering the technical entry barrier via tools like JupyterHub², we ensure that datasets remain findable, accessible, and sustainable. A detailed introduction on the workflow has been presented at several conferences including at General Assembly of the European Geosciences Union in 2024 (Ziemen et al., 2024).

1.2 Simulation setup

The simulations in nextGEMS are organized in cycles, aligned with the hackathons. In each iteration, simulations with the ICON model and IFS-FESOM were performed. In the earlier iterations, additional simulations with IFS-NEMO were contributed. The durations of the simulations and resolutions were aligned within each cycle to allow for comparison between the models, while the setups and workflows were updated with each simulation cycle to continuously improve the models and user experience.

¹<https://zarr.dev/>

²<https://jupyter.org/hub>

In the first cycle, one-year long simulations were performed. In cycle 2 the durations were extended at the cost of a slightly lower resolution. In cycle 3, 5 years at 5 km were performed. Here, ICON switched to the new hierarchical HEALPix zarr output. In the final simulations, both models were run for decades at resolutions of about 10 km. Output was provided as HEALPix. Further high-resolution simulations at about 2.5 km cover an annual cycle.

The simulations and their setup in nextGEMS are close to DestinE, as the models simulate the full globe at similar, km-scale, resolutions for comparable time spans, writing comparable variables. While the outputs are converging towards a common structure, the more exploratory nature of nextGEMS means that there still are some differences between the model variables and output frequencies. Further standardization is beyond the scope of this project and left to more operational projects such as DestinE.

1.3 Common output

To streamline data analysis and comparison across models, the HEALPix grid system has been chosen as the common analysis grid. This can be achieved in various ways, including conservative remapping, nearest neighbor interpolation or other methods, that fit the model grid and data requirements. HEALPix provides an equal-area representation that significantly simplifies analysis processes compared to the native model grids, enabling constant resolution and direct computational transformations between latitude-longitude coordinates and grid indices. Furthermore, the hierarchical nature of HEALPix allows data to be provided and analyzed at varying zoom levels. All datasets are accessible through the nextGEMS intake catalog³.

The ICON model from MPI-M outputs data consolidated into a single, comprehensive dataset, optimized for a variety of different usage scenarios through chunking in all dimensions. Data subsets, aggregations, and multi-resolution outputs are easily accessible, facilitating efficient global analyses at lower resolutions suitable for typical screen-based visualization tasks.

The IFS-FESOM model from ECMWF initially outputs data in General Regularly-distributed Information in Binary form (GRIB) format, stored in an Fields DataBase (FDB⁴). Most nextGEMS outputs are provided to users via a pseudo-zarr interface, leveraging kerchunk⁵ and gribscan⁶ (Kölling et al., 2025), being a tool developed within the context of nextGEMS for generating kerchunk reference tables from GRIB files. The latest simulation at high resolutions (2.8 km) was additionally provided as chunked zarr datasets, adhering to CF⁷ conventions for naming and structuring, hosted externally accessible via the DKRZ object stores⁸. Currently, IFS-FESOM outputs are available primarily at zoom levels 9 and 11, supporting efficient extraction and use in various analytical scenarios.

While nextGEMS aims to provide the data as Zarr due to various advantages, DestinE currently stores all output in GRIB format in an FDB. While this is most likely for backward compatibility,

³<https://github.com/nextGEMS/catalog>

⁴<https://github.com/ecmwf/fdb>

⁵<https://fsspec.github.io/kerchunk/>

⁶<https://gribscan.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁷<https://cfconventions.org/>

⁸https://eu-dkrz-1.dkrz.cloud/browser/nextgems/rechunked_ngc4008/

it limits workflow improvements and performance. On the other hand, DestinE introduced the use of a general state vector (GSV) to unify the variables present in the output, which is a great improvement on the output side.

1.4 Postprocessing and re-chunking

Zarr stores data in chunks, which are each read, written and compressed entirely, but independent from each other. When creating a dataset, one is free to choose the chunk shape. To avoid frequent re-writes in a model with time stepping, this requires to either keep many time steps in memory (which may not be large enough) before writing a chunk, or having only a small number of time steps per chunk. But as described later in this section, a small chunk size in the time-dimension can be detrimental for access performance. A possible compromise is to write data in small chunks first, and then re-chunk it in a second pass, to make it analysis-ready.

The size and shape of chunks drastically affects the practical access speed of the dataset, as decompression only works on full chunks, and thus full chunks need to be read and decompressed for data access. In the best case, the data needed directly corresponds to a couple of chunks, limiting the number of reads while allowing for some parallelism. In the worst case, each chunk consists of a lot of data that is not needed, e.g. data chunked as world maps when requiring a local time series. In this case, users would have to read many chunks, throwing most of the data away.

The chunk size is mostly a compromise between the amount of unwanted by-catch and thus wasted I/O bandwidth during reading (for large chunks) and the number of I/O operations on the underlying storage (for small chunks). In practice, chunk sizes on the order of 10 MB have proven useful when stored as files on the filesystem of the levante supercomputer. For remote access over HTTP, slightly lower values, towards 1MB seem better.

The chunk shape (i.e. the ratio of chunk sizes along different dimensions) depends on the usage pattern. To find the best chunk shape for the model output, we analyzed how ICON data is accessed in nextGEMS in (Zimmermann et al., 2024).

Figure 1: Access comparison for precipitation of the nextGEMS cycle 3 ICON simulation. The access was tracked 6 hourly for over 10 months. The x-axis denotes the time, whereas the y-axis holds every combination of frequency and zoom level. Red denotes predominantly time series style access while blue denotes predominantly global map style access. White indicates a balanced read pattern accessing a similar fraction of the grid points and time steps. Grey denotes no access at all.

An example plot of the access patterns can be seen in Figure 1. The evaluation shows that data is accessed in various ways, from a full time series at a single location to a global map for a single point in time. We therefore rechunked the ICON output with a compromise, having decent performance for both access patterns.

Low zoom levels hold only space aggregated information, reducing memory footprint and therefore allowing to store a full variable in a chunk. This speeds up global time series analysis significantly compared to storing the same data in daily chunks, as can be seen in Figure 2. The re-chunking ensures chunks of decent size for all variables, zoom levels and frequencies. As this is done for ICON since cycle 3. We have also converted IFS production data to zarr and therefore also introduced this kind of chunking, improving access performance.

In contrast to traditional data access systems such as MARS or OPeNDAP, where internal data storage details are abstracted from the user, exposing the Zarr interface directly to end users ensures that client libraries have explicit knowledge of the internal chunking and storage layout. This transparency is a significant advantage, as it enables users and client-side tools to make informed choices about access patterns and optimize performance accordingly. By aligning the data provision strategy with modern, open formats like zarr, NextGEMS empowers advanced workflows and facilitates more efficient, flexible, and reproducible data analysis.

With an eye on DestinE, we strongly recommend to switch from GRIB to Zarr to allow n-dimensional chunked data storage and access for fast analysis. This would not only lower the barrier for working with the data but also increases performance drastically.

Figure 2: Global mean of near-surface-air temperature (tas). The time to compute this plot was improved from 9 minutes to a few milliseconds.

The code for plotting the global time series of near-surface-air temperature in Figure 2 can be seen in Listing 1. More information of the access and data provision will be given in the following subsection. While the old workflow would be analyzing the data on model resolution without any improved chunking, this would take around 9 minutes to plot. This already improves with rechunking to 2 minutes and 31 seconds on the highest zoom level. When using zoom level 0 with optimized chunking, this plot can be created in a few milliseconds.

Listing 1: Accessing data from catalog

```
import intake
cat = intake.open_catalog("https://data.nextgems-h2020.eu/online.yaml")
ds = cat.ICDN.ngc4008.to_dask()
ds.tas.mean(dim="cell").plot()
```

For the IFS data, re-chunking is not possible due to the data stored in GRIB, where chunk size and shape are immutable defined by the GRIB specification. However, the plotting of global mean of near-surface-air temperature of IFS is still improved due to two provided zoom levels, where it takes an hour for zoom level 11 and only 30 seconds on zoom level 7. With converting the GRIB via FDB to pure Zarr, chunk limitations were overcome and could be optimized as well. This has been done for the final nextGEMS simulation and is served via the DKRZ object store in the online catalog. Time series plots of IFS data from Zarr in an object store is at least 3 times faster than accessing via FDB directly from the file system. For plots where only limited spatial data is needed to be loaded, Zarr was up to 20 times faster. This is even more impressive, as the Zarr data is stored on an object store, which has more latency and less bandwidth than direct file system access on an FDB. For zoom level 11 a time series plot of for a small region takes 8 seconds on Zarr and more than 30 minutes with the FDB.

1.5 Data provision and catalogs

Data is provided via catalogs, which makes data findable and accessible. Application for Quality Assessment (AQUA⁹) is also using catalogs in DestinE to provide data access. Catalogs do not only make different data formats accessible via a common interface but also introduce a layer between the physical data storage and the user accessing the data, enabling data providers moving data sets, refining or fixing them without the user to notice in the best case or changing their way of accessing the data. Catalogs also enable data providers to use different storage tiers depending on the actual data set usage. In comparison with an energy efficient cold storage like a tape archive, an object store could be seen as a warm storage, offering decent access speed without any account at DKRZ. For regularly used or newly produced data-sets, the `lustre`¹⁰ file system takes care of providing hot access. While this is currently managed manually, there are efforts to automate moving data between different storage tiers. For large-scale data transfers (especially for machine learning), it has proven useful to first pack the data and thus reduce the overhead in the copy process. In the preparation of the global hackathon (6.1), `rclone`¹¹ has proven useful as well¹².

JupyterHub is another crucial tool for low barrier access to the data. There is no shell usage required to work on an HPC anymore. There is also no additional software needed besides a standard web browser. With an extensive Jupyter kernel, data analysis can start with a few lines of code.

Listing 2: Accessing data from catalog

```
import intake
import easygems.healpix as egh
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
cat = intake.open_catalog("https://data.nextgems-h2020.eu/online.yaml")
experiment = cat.ICON["ngc4008"]
data = experiment(time="P1D", zoom=5).to_dask()
ax = egh.healpix_show(data.tas.sel(time="2021-01-01"), cmap='inferno', dpi=300)
plt.colorbar(ax, fraction=0.025)
```

Listing 2 demonstrates how easy access to large datasets of climate data can be achieved. It is worth mentioning, that the online catalog lists data sets, which are served to the web and can therefore be accessed from anywhere. During the nextGEMS hackathons we provided matching Python environments on the Levante¹³ supercomputer, a specification for a similar working environment was provided in the run-up of the global hackathon¹⁴. The provision of multiple zoom levels, makes it viable to prototype an algorithm on a coarse resolution version of the data and use significant HPC resources only for the final result on a fine resolution. The following images demonstrate the use of the different zoom levels:

⁹<https://github.com/DestinE-Climate-DT/AQUA>

¹⁰<https://www.lustre.org/>

¹¹<https://rclone.org>

¹²https://github.com/digital-earths-global-hackathon/tools/tree/main/dataset_transfer

¹³<https://www.dkrz.de/en/systems/hpc/hlre-4-levante?>

¹⁴https://github.com/digital-earths-global-hackathon/tools/blob/main/python_envs

Figure 3: Results of listing 2, near-surface air temperature for zoom level 5(3a) and zoom level 9(3b)

Figures 3a and 3b demonstrate how zoom level 5 and 9 are expressed. It is to mention, that the next higher zoom level hold 4 times more data. Therefore 3b holds $4^4 = 256$ times more data than 3a. This drastically reduces the time to plot when lower resolution is sufficient. As a side-benefit, it enables users to save computing resources and thus is also advantageous in terms of energy consumption. The provisioning of data at the full hierarchy of zoom levels is a great improvement to previous access to a bulk of data, that was only provided at the highest resolution and every subsample had to be manually created. As every coarsening reduces the data by a factor of 4, the whole zoom hierarchy only adds 30% to the data, which is a fair cost considering the vast time savings in the analysis. As both ICON and IFS datasets are provided on the same grid, a comparison between the two can be done with a few lines of code as follows.

Listing 3: Comparing ICON to IFS

```
import intake
import easygems.healpix as egh
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
cat = intake.open_catalog("https://data.nextgems-h2020.eu/online.yaml")
ifs = cat.IFS['IFS_2.8-FESOM_5-production-CF'].to_dask()
icon = cat.ICON["d3hp003"](time="P1D", zoom=7).to_dask()
ifs_tas = ifs["tas"].sel(time="2020-03").mean(dim="time")
icon_tas = icon["tas"].sel(time="2020-03").mean(dim="time")
diff = (ifs_tas - icon_tas)
ax = egh.healpix_show(diff, cmap='RdBu_r', vmin=-10, vmax=10)
plt.colorbar(ax, fraction=0.025)
```


Figure 4: results of listing 3. Comparison of Near-surface-air temperature from ICON with IFS.

1.6 Documentation and hackathons

Hackathons have proven themselves to be an important part of the workflow. They encourage sharing of best practices, exchanging information and improve education on accessing the datasets. Hackathons are also a great stress test, to reliably serve the datasets. They also create an environment for exchange across sub-disciplinary teams, enabling sharing of best practices not only within a certain team but for the whole community of users.

Hackathons are not only a great option for users to get to work with the data but also enable exchange with the data providers and model developers. Beside Hackathons, extensive documentation is indispensable. In nextGEMS we introduced `easy.gems`¹⁵ which holds descriptions of simulations and instructions for the efficient use of the new datasets. This has reduced the need for support during the hackathons drastically, as users can work from the curated examples provided here. Furthermore, for the hackathons, we created GitHub repositories, where code can be shared with a low entrance barrier.

With the opportunity to use JupyterHub and examples that can be copy pasted to it, users have a unprecedented low barrier to entry getting started to work with the data. The extensive documentation does not only help users use the new workflows but also help understanding the bigger picture. With this being successful across the board in the nextGEMS hackathons, the new workflow was also introduced to the first Global Hackathon¹⁶. Teams around the world made efforts to convert their climate data to HEALPix in Zarr. With 10 models provided for over 600 users around the world, the first Global Hackathon was a great way of disseminating this kind of workflow and received predominantly positive feedback. We thus expect these workflows to get more traction globally.

¹⁵<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/>

¹⁶<https://digital-earths-global-hackathon.github.io/hk25/>

1.7 Analysis support libraries

While `easy.gems` is an extensive documentation, `easygems`¹⁷ is the corresponding python module, that covers basic functionality needed for the new workflows. This includes a fast plot function for data on HEALPix coordinates as well as regridding to and from different kinds of grids. While it is recommended to stay in HEALPix, users had their previous scripts often fine tuned for latitude longitude grids or the very specific model output grids. If a change to HEALPix was not viable in a short time, like a hackathon, users could regrid their desired variables and were not excluded. Also CDO¹⁸ is able to work with HEALPix and was used to work with the nextGEMS data. The majority used JupyterHub and interactive python coding to analyze the data on the nextGEMS Hackathons. Another helpful tool is UXarray¹⁹, which extends xarrays support of rectilinear grids by all kinds of structured and unstructured grids like HEALPix.

2 Dissemination and uptake

The Global hackathon is the biggest dissemination event with global uptake for the approaches developed here. DestinE is also a prominent example of uptake, even if not implementing all parts of the workflow described here. The usage of catalogs and the definition of a GSV for simulation output improved the workflow to work with the data. There is also postprocessing to a common analysis grid present. While HEALPix is not new, and was used cosmology for over two decade, its use in climate science is novel. However, tools like CDO and UXarray have quickly installed support for HEALPix.

(Magin et al., 2024) make satellite data also accessible in HEALPix via `xdggs`²⁰.

3 Deliverable timeliness

On time.

4 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

None

¹⁷<https://pypi.org/project/easygems/>

¹⁸<https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo>

¹⁹<https://uxarray.readthedocs.io/en/stable/user-guide/healpix.html>

²⁰<https://xdggs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/tutorials/healpix.html>

5 Sustainability

This workflow has been taken up in DestinE and other projects, such as WarmWorld.

6 Full track of dissemination activities

As part of the H2020 NextGEMS project, six hackathons were organized to engage the scientific community, foster collaboration, and facilitate hands-on work with project data and tools. Each hackathon focused on key scientific challenges and promoted knowledge exchange between model developers and users.

- **Cycle 1 Hackathon, 19th –22nd October, 2021 (Berlin, Germany)**

The inaugural NextGEMS hackathon gathered around 80 participants for an intensive, hands-on project meeting coinciding with the completion of the first Cycle 1 high-resolution simulations from ICON and IFS. Participants collaborated in small teams to address key questions in Storms and Radiation, Storms and Land, Storms and Ocean, and Storms and Society. The event provided an invaluable opportunity for the community to familiarize themselves with the new simulation data, and the insights gained directly influenced the design and focus of subsequent Cycle 2 simulations.

- **Cycle 2 Hackathon, 28th June – 2nd July, 2022 (Vienna, Austria)**

The Cycle 2 hackathon in Vienna brought together nearly 100 participants for a dynamic week of data exploration, collaboration, and community building. The event combined intensive hands-on work with the latest storm-resolving model outputs from ICON and IFS, workshops on advanced data handling, and evening lectures on scientific challenges and future directions in high-resolution modeling. The hackathon also featured a focused challenge on renewable energy, involving early stage researchers and stakeholders from the sector. The collaborative efforts and knowledge exchange during this event helped shape the scientific direction for the subsequent simulation cycle.

- **Cycle 3 Hackathon, 29th May – 2nd June (Barcelona, Spain)**

The Cycle 3 hackathon in Madrid was the largest NextGEMS event to date, welcoming 140 participants from across Europe and Senegal, and fostering collaboration with partner projects such as MULMOD, DestinE, EERIE, and WarmWorld. Participants worked intensively with the latest Cycle 3 model outputs, including the first use of the HEALPix grid for ICON and new model components like aerosols and biogeochemistry. The hackathon also featured workshops and lectures by leading scientists, covering topics such as biogeochemical modeling and extreme rainfall observations. The event promoted interdisciplinary exchange, tackled new scientific challenges, and contributed to the ongoing development of digital twin concepts for climate information services.

- **km-scale Hackathon, 4th – 8th March, 2024 (Hamburg, Germany)**

The km-scale Hackathon in Hamburg marked a new era, with over 130 participants from diverse backgrounds collaborating to apply advanced Earth system models in a range of scientific contexts. Co-organized by the EERIE, WarmWorld, and nextGEMS projects, the

event fostered interdisciplinary knowledge exchange and coproduction. The program featured talks on transforming scientific knowledge into action, advances in ICON and IFS models, and new approaches to international climate collaboration. In addition to scientific sessions, participants engaged in side events including communal dinners and visits to research facilities. The hackathon concluded with thematic group discussions and a celebration of International Women’s Day, highlighting both the achievements of the community and the path forward for collaborative climate science.

- **Hazard Hackathon, 14th – 18th October, 2024 (Wageningen, Netherland)**

The Hazard Hackathon, co-organized by Wageningen University and Research and the University of Bern, brought together scientists and industry professionals for a week focused on natural hazards and climate risks. Participants worked intensively on topics such as extreme precipitation, wildfire risk, and renewable energy production, supported by workshops and keynote presentations from experts in model evaluation and Earth system fire modeling. The event fostered valuable networking and collaboration across disciplines, and included industry engagement sessions to explore practical applications of nextGEMS data for energy and food sectors. Highlights included the “Energy Storylines” workshop and a communal hackathon dinner, reinforcing both the scientific and community spirit of the event.

- **Final Countdown Hackathon, 25th-28th March, 2025 (Stockholm, Sweden)**

The Final Countdown Hackathon in Stockholm concluded the NextGEMS project’s series of collaborative events, bringing together over 70 participants at the Swedish Museum of Natural History. This hackathon focused on applying Storm-Resolving Earth System Models to real-world challenges in the renewable energy sector, with active participation from industry stakeholders and climate scientists. Sessions addressed future energy scenarios for 2050, data-driven forecasting of extreme events, and the broader impacts of climate extremes. Reflections on project achievements underscored advances in model development, km-scale modeling, and data infrastructure, laying the groundwork for future European climate initiatives. The event highlighted NextGEMS’s enduring legacy and the continued evolution of climate modeling beyond the project’s formal conclusion.

6.1 Global km-scale Hackathon (WCRP)

Held from 12-16 May 2025 as part of the WCRP Digital Earths Lighthouse Activity²¹, this global hackathon built directly on the legacy of NextGEMS by scaling its collaborative, data-centric model to a worldwide, distributed event.

Across ten regional nodes on five continents (including a Hamburg node at DKRZ/MPI-M), over 600 participants ranging from climate scientists to developers concurrently on sub 5 km resolution Earth system model outputs from ICON, IFS-FESOM, NICAM, NCAR-MPAS, CAS and more²². Goal of this hackathon was to introduce the new workflow with zarr, HEALPix and catalogs to make climate data broadly accessible and also easy to compare on a common analysis grid.

²¹<https://www.wcrp-esmo.org/activities/wcrp-global-km-scale-hackathon-2025>

²²<https://digital-earths-global-hackathon.github.io/hk25/simulations/>

This hackathon marks a major milestone in extending the NextGEMS approach from project-specific events to a globally coordinated effort, reinforcing its role in shaping future digital twin and Earth system modeling initiatives.

easy.gems

We provide the documentation site `easy.gems` (sec. 1.6), which was created, elaborated and extended during the H2020 project in order to sustainably document the new workflow and provide examples of best practises. However, it has to be mentioned, that personal data support was present at all times to answer questions that `easy.gems` could not. With the completion of the H2020 project, the personal data support will diminish but `easy.gems` will be continued. The idea of `easy.gems` is a reliable source of information for easy access and workflows. This documentation is aimed to live across several projects like nextGEMS, esiwace, warmworld, eerie and others.

7 Full track of publications and IP

Hohenegger, C., et al. (2023). “ICON-Sapphire: simulating the components of the Earth system and their interactions at kilometer and subkilometer scales.” *Geoscientific Model Development* 16(2), pp. 779–811. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-779-2023>

Rackow, T., et al. (2022). “Storm-resolving simulations with IFS-NEMO/FESOM in the NextGEMS project.” Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-10757>

Rackow, T., et al. (2023). “Storm- and eddy-resolving simulations with IFS-FESOM/NEMO at the kilometre scale.” Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-16453>

Modali, K., et al. (2024). “A cascaded framework for unified access to and analysis of kilometer scale global simulations across a federation of data centers.” Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-19677>

Ziemen, F., Kölling, T., & Kluft, L. (2024). “Data access for km-scale resolution models.” Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-18256>

Zimmermann, J., Ziemen, F., & Kölling, T. (2024). “Data access patterns of km-scale resolution models.” Presented at EGU General Assembly, Vienna. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-17150>

Rackow, T., et al. (2025). “Multi-year simulations at kilometre scale with the Integrated Forecasting System coupled to FESOM2.5 and NEMOv3.4.” *Geoscientific Model Development*

18(1), pp. 33–69. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-18-33-2025>

Publicated data sets

Bastin, S., A. Koldunov, H. Haak, N. Koldunov, S. Danilov, J. Jungclaus, M. Jochum, M. A. Mrozowska, T. Fischer, M. Dengler, N. Brüggemann, O. Gutjahr, and M. S. Specht (2023a). High frequency tropical Atlantic data from vertical mixing sensitivity runs with FESOM and ICON-O (nextGEMS WP6). World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) at DKRZ. https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_WP6oc

Bastin, S., et al. (Aug. 2023b). nextGEMS: Output of the WP6 ocean vertical mixing sensitivity runs (timeseries). Version 1.0. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8225706>

Grayson, K. M. (June 2024). nextGEMS cycle3 datasets: statistical summaries for streamed data from climate simulations. Version v3. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12533197>

Koldunov, N., T. Kölling, X. Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia, T. Rackow, R. Redler, D. Sidorenko, K.-H. Wieners, and F. A. Ziemer (2023). nextGEMS: output of the model development cycle 3 simulations for ICON and IFS. World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) at DKRZ. https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc3

Proske, U., N. Brüggemann, J. P. Gärtner, O. Gutjahr, H. Haak, D. Putrasahan, and K.-H. Wieners (Sept. 2024). Data and scripts for the publication “A case for open communication of bugs in climate models”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14220612>

Rackow, T., T. Becker, and X. Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia (Jan. 2025). Namelist files and settings for 30-year km-scale nextGEMS Cycle 4 production simulations with IFS-FESOM. Version v1. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14725225>

Rackow, T., X. Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia, and T. Becker (Nov. 2023). Namelist files and settings for multi-year km-scale nextGEMS Cycle 3 simulations with IFS-FESOM/NEMO. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10221652>

Uribe, A., F. Bender, and T. Maurtisen (Nov. 2024). Replication Data for figures in: Constraining net long-term climate feedback from satellite-observed internal variability possible by the mid-2030s. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14219552>

Weiss, P., R. Herbert, and P. Stier (Dec. 2024b). Data for “ICON-HAM-lite: simulating the Earth system with interactive aerosols at kilometer scales”. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14393773>

Wieners, K.-H., T. Rackow, R. Aguridan, T. Becker, S. Beyer, S. K. Cheedela, N.-A. Dreier, J. F. Engels, M. Esch, C. Frauen, D. Klocke, T. Kölling, X. Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia, D. Pu-

trasahan, D. Sidorenko, R. Schnur, B. Stevens, and J. Zimmermann (2024). nextGEMS: output of the production simulations for ICON and IFS. World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) at DKRZ.

Wieners, K.-H., F. A. Ziemer, N. Koldunov, X. Predruzo-Bagazgoitia, T. Rackow, R. Redler, D. Sidorenko, and T. Kölling (Mar. 2023). nextGEMS: output of the model development cycle 2 simulations for ICON and IFS. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc2

8 References

- Górski, K. M., E. Hivon, A. J. Banday, B. D. Wandelt, F. K. Hansen, M. Reinecke, and M. Bartelmann (2005). “HEALPix: A Framework for High-Resolution Discretization and Fast Analysis of Data Distributed on the Sphere”. In: *The Astrophysical Journal* 622.2, p. 759. DOI: [10.1086/427976](https://doi.org/10.1086/427976).
- Kölling, T., L. Kluft, and T. Rackow (2025). *gribscan*. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10625188](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10625188).
- Magin, J., B. Bovy, J.-M. Delouis, A. Fouilloux, A. Coca-Castro, R. Abernathey, P. Strobl, A. Kmoch, and T. E. Odaka (2024). *Advancing Geospatial Data Analysis with XDGGS*. Version 1.0. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13934967](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13934967).
- Ziemen, F., T. Kölling, and L. Kluft (2024). “Data access for km-scale resolution models”. In: *EGU General Assembly*. Vienna. DOI: [10.5194/egusphere-egu24-18256](https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-18256).
- Zimmermann, J., F. Ziemen, and T. Kölling (2024). “Data access patterns of km-scale resolution models”. In: *EGU General Assembly*. Vienna. DOI: [10.5194/egusphere-egu24-17150](https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-17150).